

Smart planning tools for Renewable Energy Communities: an overview on the Italian case

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Abstract—Energy Communities (ECs) are an emerging policy instrument to support the increasing participation of citizens in energy matters. However, their optimal sizing requires an appropriate estimate of demand, renewable sources, and technical expertise, which are time-consuming and require trained personnel. For these reasons, digital support decision tools have been proposed to support decision-making, yet guidance on their trade-offs is still missing. This paper analyzes recent platforms to design ECs in an Italian context. Particular attention is given to standardization in data collection and input, as well as the integration of optimization techniques for models. The absence of such features in models under consideration limits their potential for enhancing understanding and application in decision-making processes that are aimed at increasing the future benefits associated with the operation and management of the energy community. This paper emphasizes the significance of taking into account economic, environmental, and technological factors when calculating the ideal sizing of renewable energy systems. The authors also discuss the importance of open data and collaboration in developing high-quality modelling tools in the energy sector. The findings of this study underscore the need for continued advancements in energy modelling methodologies, as well as the importance of integrating optimization techniques within energy modelling frameworks.

Index Terms—renewable, energy community, energy model, tool, sizing

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

The transition towards renewable energy is essential to address the increasing energy demand and mitigate climate change impacts. The European Commission passed the "Clean Energy for All Europeans" package in 2019, aimed at modifying the European energy policy and fostering increased renewable penetration. The Renewable Energy Directive Recast (RED II) established the Renewable Energy Community (REC) as a new paradigm for empowering citizens by involving them in the energy transition, [1]. The REC is intended to aid in deploying renewable energy sources and increase the public acceptance of renewable throughout Europe. Citizens can use RECs to create community energy initiatives, pool individual contributions, and become active prosumers of the power system. In such communities, households or small businesses collectively own and operate renewable energy systems, and share the generated energy among the group members.

The first RECs established in Italy since 2019 have highlighted that there are three typical phases for the development of a REC project, namely "design", "creation," and "operation" [2]. The goal of the design phase is to develop a technical, economic/financial, and social proposal for the REC projects and engage stakeholders. The purpose of the creation phase is to legally establish the REC and install the new generation facilities that will be integrated into the community's framework. Finally, the operation phase entails day-to-day actions to monitor, organize, and control resources to ensure that design performance and project goals are met. In conclusion, a REC project entails a series of interconnected and interdependent sub-steps that necessitate a wide range of competencies, such as legal, administrative, technical, social, and financial.

The implementation of REC projects is expensive and challenging due to complex processes and high competencies required. In this context, the goal of smart planning tools is to reduce costs associated with the design phase and provide transparent, automated, or semi-automated methods to guide and assist REC designers throughout the project proposal. Moreover, the availability of open-source smart planning tools allows groups of citizens to establish small RECs for which the costs of professional design would be too high.

B. Related work

In this section, we provide a comprehensive overview of the related work in the field of freeware smart planning tools and design methods for RECs. We explore studies and research efforts conducted subsequent to the implementation of the Milleproroghe transient regulatory framework in 2019, which aimed to transpose the RED II EU directive in Italy. This transient framework introduced the adoption of a virtual model for quantifying the shared energy among community members. At the moment of writing, the approval of the definitive framework, the Italian Decree-Law n. 199 of 2021, is under discussion. This definitive framework, while incorporating certain modifications, reaffirms the utilization of the virtual model upon which this study, the literature, and the cited digital platforms are based.

Minuto et al. in [2] conduct a comparative analysis of 30 software tools and platforms for Renewable Energy Communities (RECs). The study identifies a list of services needed by

RECs at different stages of REC project implementation and evaluates the tools based on the presence of these services. The platforms analyzed include offerings from private companies, national agencies, and research projects, encompassing both European-wide and Italian market-specific solutions. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the only study that analyzes the software platforms released on the Italian market following the implementation of the RED II.

Several models and methods have been presented in the literature to evaluate energy flows and the optimal size of photovoltaic (PV) plants serving RECs. Coletta et al. [3] introduced a method for optimal sizing of PV generators to maximize the Net Present Value (NPV) of REC projects over a 20-year time horizon. Their approach aims to serve REC users efficiently. Another significant contribution by Todeschi et al. [4] focuses on optimizing grid-connected PV battery systems in urban areas. They employ Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithms to find the ideal system configuration, resulting in increased self-sufficiency and consumption while minimizing net present costs. Zatti et al. [5] proposed a methodology for the design optimization of energy communities by integrating various technologies such as boilers, heat pumps, PVs, and thermal storage. The optimization problem is formulated as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem to determine the optimal size of energy assets. In a similar vein, Cutore et al. [6] developed a linearized method for sizing PV battery systems, which optimizes the NPV of RECs. Their work incorporates the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle for the design of REC projects. Furthermore, within the realm of REC design, a branch of literature examines and proposes performance evaluation parameters. Cutore et al. [7] suggested economic, social, and environmental indicators for comprehensive evaluation of REC designs. Ghiani et al. [8] put forth a list of indicators to evaluate REC performance, with potential application during the design phase to offer recommendations for performance improvement. Moreover, the authors utilized these parameters to analyze the economic and energy performance of the Magliano Alpi REC during its initial year of operation [9]. These studies have been employed in real-life case studies conducted in Italy, thereby yielding valuable insights for developers of smart planning tools.

The existing methods for optimizing Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) have the advantage of being generalized, but they lack customization for complex business models. These models often involve diverse remuneration schemes for installations owned by the REC and private individuals contributing their generation. Additionally, the presence of an aggregator further complicates matters. To address these challenges, Fioriti et al. [10] propose an optimization problem that considers crucial factors such as mitigating the agency problem, ensuring equitable reward distribution, estimating fair compensation for aggregator services, and defining appropriate exit clauses. By integrating these considerations, the proposed optimization model provides a comprehensive framework for determining the optimal size of a Continuous REC.

Finally, we empathise the importance of open data, it plays a pivotal role in the advancement of sophisticated modelling tools in the energy sector, such as smart planning tools. As discussed by Pfenninger et al. [11], the availability of open access to models and data is indispensable to ensure the principles of transparency, peer review, repeatability, and traceability, which are fundamental tenets of scientific inquiry that contribute to the production of high-quality scientific outcomes. By making datasets and reference models openly accessible and subject to collaborative development, the workload can be distributed more widely, encompassing both academic and governmental spheres. Moreover, the dissemination of open data fosters productivity gains through collaborative burden sharing, thereby enabling researchers to avoid unnecessary duplication of efforts and facilitate mutual learning.

C. Contributions

This paper makes several original research contributions, as described in the following. The lack of a review and comparison of the various Italian available modelling tools on energy communities presents a significant obstacle in the creation and optimization of sustainable energy systems. Policymakers, academics, and community leaders may struggle to make educated judgments about energy community efforts unless they have a thorough understanding of the instrument's strengths and weaknesses. A full examination and comparison of these modelling tools would provide useful information about their capabilities, accuracy, and relevance to certain scenarios. It would allow stakeholders to pick the best tool for their needs, improve collaboration, and encourage the effective planning and implementation of energy community initiatives in Italy.

In the field of energy communities, there is also an urgent need to compare the features of various modelling tools and to build a consistent framework for input and output. A comparison like this would allow stakeholders to assess the merits and limitations of each instrument, while standardization would improve interoperability and data exchange, enabling more effective collaboration and decision-making in the search for sustainable energy solutions. The open nature of modelling tools for renewable energy groups is critical. Researchers, politicians, and community members can actively participate in the development and refinement of models by offering transparent and accessible tools. This promotes knowledge sharing, spurs innovation, and eventually leads to more accurate and inclusive depictions of renewable energy groups, promoting their growth and general adoption.

D. Paper organization

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II lists the freeware tools for RECs considered in this study and describes the methodology used to compare them; Section III describes the key features of the digital platforms under comparison, including their functionalities and usability; in Section IV main results obtained from the assessment are

TABLE I
OPEN SOURCE DIGITAL PLATFORMS FOR REC DESIGN

Tool name	Agency	Reference
GSE Simulator	GSE	[12]
RECON	ENEA	[13]
ROSE	MAPS	[14]
HEXERGY APP	HEXERGY	[15]

indicated; the last section summarizes main research findings and presents our conclusions.

II. METHODS AND MATERIALS

This section aims to provide an overview of the types of services offered by open-source digital platforms to design RECs and collective self-consumption schemes (CSCs), considering the Italian legal framework. To the best of the authors' knowledge, at the time of writing, there are four open-source digital platforms on the web draw to assist the developers in the design and planning of energy communities, whose references are provided in Table I. The four digital platforms considered in this study were developed by the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), by the Italian public entity for incentive programs for renewable energy sources, known as Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (GSE), and by two private companies. There are several other platforms for REC design, developed within European research projects or by private companies, which were not included in this study because they either are not designed for the Italian REC incentive system or do not have an open-access version.

The evaluation criteria of the digital platforms were identified through an analysis of the CER design process described in Subsection II-A. The analysis was carried out based on the direct experience of the authors in CER design and by consulting the relevant scientific literature [2] [6]. The evaluation criteria aim to assess the presence or absence of specific services as reported in Subsection II-B by the platforms, without assigning any merit grades.

A. Description of Design step of a REC project

Designing a REC under the Italian regulatory framework is a process that begins with the intention of a promoter to establish a REC and concludes with a technical project, an investment proposal, and a social project. The promoter can typically be a public administration, an energy player (such as an energy services company), or a group of citizens, and they may undertake the design study themselves or entrust it to a third party. The promoter steps of the design process could be resumed as follow:

- Preliminary study aimed at determining the desired REC legal status, the geographical scope, funding, and the economic, social, and environmental objectives;
- Initiating an active engagement of various stakeholders, through a territory-wide communication campaign;

- Collection from stakeholders relevant data on energy consumption, existing renewable energy installations and availability for new installations.
- Analysis of the information provided by users regarding their consumption and production. Typical data collected include the total annual energy demand, consumption categorized by time-of-use tariff bands, total monthly consumption, monthly consumption categorized by time-of-use tariff bands, and hourly consumption records.
- Verifying whether the Point of Delivery (POD) of interested parties falls within the proximity constraints specified for the REC.
- Investment proposal formulation based on estimations of the REC's capital expenditures (CAPEX), operational expenditures (OPEX) and revenues. The purchase and installation of generation systems are accounted for, considering a twenty-year price projection since the premium tariff is ensured for 20 years by law.
 - Regarding CAPEX, the expenses considered include the acquisition and installation of the REC's owned generation systems, legal costs associated with establishing the REC's legal entity, and design expenses for the REC.
 - In terms of OPEX, the developer factors in the management costs of the REC, encompassing treasury management, onboarding and offboarding procedures for new members, and shared asset control. Additionally, routine maintenance costs for the REC's owned generation systems and extraordinary maintenance costs, such as inverter replacements, are considered.
 - The revenue estimated for the REC comprises the premium tariff granted to shared energy, and the income generated from selling the electricity produced. The savings resulting from direct self-consumption should be accounted to individual owners.
- Presentation of the technical plan, the financial proposal, and the social plan to all stakeholders.

B. Evaluation Criteria

The tools listed in Table I are evaluated by defining a set of KPIs divided into four categories: Output, Input, Optimization, and Openness. The KPIs are reported in Table II.

The first category, Output, includes the results that the platforms provide after the simulation. The Input category lists the inputs considered by the software to obtain the results. The Optimization category reviews the energy resources that the software can use for the optimal sizing of the REC and

the ability to customize objective functions and constraints during optimization. Lastly, Openness lists the KPIs useful for evaluating how well the platforms adhere to open standards, models, and formulations accessible to the public.

III. DIGITAL PLATFORM DESCRIPTION

The following section examines the four open access models and highlights relevant features, accessibility, and aspect discussed in Section II.

A. GSE Simulator

The first platform provided by GSE [12], allows users to access the platform without the need for a login. However, GSE lacks the capability to store information for future projects, which might limit its long-term usefulness. The tool optimizes the configuration of RECs and CSCs to maximize the self-consumed electricity based on the available surface of each member. The output of the GSE simulation tool is a web page that provides an overview of the technical and economic parameters, including projections of annual revenues, taxation, and maintenance costs. These results can also be downloaded as a PDF document for ease of sharing and reference.

To utilize the GSE simulation tool, users must provide a range of inputs, including their overall yearly electricity consumption and the yearly needs of users connected to the renewable system and the share of yearly consumption during daily hours. The tool allows users to optionally specify the type of surface available for photovoltaic systems, including up to four surfaces with a range of options for each surface, such as type of shadow, the inclination and orientation of panels. Users can also set different tariffs, specify the share for each range, and set the power allowed for the user.

B. Simulator ENEA: RECON

The ENEA Simulator, also known as RECON, is a web app that requires users to create a profile with credentials upon their first login [13]. ENEA's tool is noteworthy for its ability to export data in a JSON file format, enabling easy integration with other systems or applications. The simulator allows users to create REC, CSC, or individual self-consumption projects and investigate different design scenarios with related graphs which present the 20-year financial plan and the aggregated energy flows within the community.

The platform employs customization of users based on their unique consumption patterns. The clustering is performed by considering factors such as appliance characteristics, hours of usage, and building types. It accounts for optional technical input such as panel angles and the annual loss of efficiency caused by shading dust, and weather conditions or financial inputs such as investment costs, maintenance expenses, discount rates, and inflation rates. However, RECON does not allow to consider a configuration with more than one PV plant. Overall cash flows are calculated, providing a view of revenue streams, operating costs, and potential financial returns throughout the project's lifespan. The model also quantifies environmental savings. Furthermore, key financial indicators such as NPV,

IRR, and PBT are derived, offering crucial insights into the economic viability, and profitability of the proposed initiatives.

C. Simulator MAPS: ROSE

This smart planning tool is a web app accessible through a common browser [14]. Users are prompted to create a profile with credentials upon their first login. The free version of the simulator enables the designer to understand energy flows and some financial parameters.

Each configuration is characterized by a set of inputs: the energy data of consumers, prosumers, and producers, the estimated value of the premium tariff rates, and the estimate of electricity market prices. The designer can select the number and type of consumers, in the free version is possible to consider only domestic type of users. Similarly, for prosumers, the designer can select the number and type of their consumption but cannot input specific data points. Producers can be characterized by a photovoltaic system and a battery energy storage system (BESS), without an associated load. The platform is capable of estimating the hourly production of a PV plant based on the project's location and nominal power.

The results dashboard is divided into four sections: REC, consumers, prosumers, and producers. In the REC section, the available outputs include an analysis of REC energy flows, economic revenue from energy sales, and an estimation of revenue from shared energy incentives. The consumer section contains the hourly consumption profiles. In the prosumers section, hourly production and consumption profiles are given, as well as the profiles for direct self-consumption of individual prosumers. Finally, in the producer's section, it is possible to observe PV production, as well as the charging and discharging of the BESS.

D. Simulator HEXERGY: HEXERGY APP

The HEXERGY Simulator is a platform designed for simulating different scenarios of RECs [15]. To access the platform, users are required to log in, even for the free version. The main objective of the simulator is to provide users with a tool to analyze and evaluate the feasibility of their REC projects. One of the key features of HEXERGY is the ability to select different generation locations, allowing users to assess the potential of renewable energy resources in specific areas.

In addition to location selection, HEXERGY offers optional features for various technical and financial inputs. Users can input parameters such as the size and type of renewable energy systems, energy consumption profiles, and financial parameters like investment costs and tariff rates. These inputs enable users to customize their simulations and evaluate the performance and economic viability of their REC projects.

The output of the HEXERGY Simulator includes KPIs that provide a comprehensive overview of the project's performance. These KPIs allow users to assess important metrics such as self-consumption ratios, greenhouse gas emissions reduction, and energy fed to the grid compared to energy withdrawal from the network. Additionally, the simulator generates two graphs that visualize energy fluxes and business

TABLE II
ALL KPI

	ID	Feature name	Description	GSE	ROSE	ENEA	HEXE
Input	1	Multiple RES locations	Set different locations for RES; Set different datasets (e.g. PVGIS, ENEA, etc...)				X
	2	RES efficiency	RES production (e.g. for PV Set azimuth for each PV system; Set the level of shadow for each PV system)	X		X	X
	3	Fiscal Scheme	Wide variety of fiscal revenues and expenses for REC or CSC	X		X	X
	4	Energy components CAPEX	Set arbitrary components CAPEX; Suggest typical values based on reference size	X		X	X
	5	Energy components OPEX	Set arbitrary components OPEX; Suggest typical values based on reference size			X	X
	6	Extraordinary maintenance	Set the frequency of maintenance for different components (e.g. Inverter substitution)			X	
	7	Battery storage enhancement	Add battery system optionally to increase self-consumption of electricity	X	X	X	X
	8	Time framework of load input	Set different load information for all users (e.g. yearly consumption, monthly, hourly)		X	X	X
	9	Archetype of load user	Set different load profiles for all users (e.g. residential, commercial, industrial, services)		X	X	
	10	Energy market price sensitivity	Set different prices for energy injected into the grid; Set different prices for withdrawing electricity from the grid		X		X
	11	Different voltage levels	Set different levels of voltage for all prosumers	X			
	12	Multiple scenarios	Give users possibilities to set different scenarios in the same use case (e.g. number of users, etc...)				X
Output	1	Investment proposal for REC or CSC	Investment plan for REC or CSC (e.g. 20-year financial plan with discounted cash flow)	X		X	X
	2	Investment proposal for members	Investment plan for individual members with financial (NPV, IRR and Payback time)				
	3	Energy fluxes for REC or CSC	An aggregated description of electricity fluxes (e.g. self-consumption, grid injection, etc...)	X	X	X	X
	4	Energy fluxes for prosumers	Description of energy fluxes for individual prosumers			X	
	5	Hourly resolution	Hourly resolution of the energy analysis for RES or CSC and individual members		X		X
	6	Performance metrics of REC or CSC	Indicator to evaluate the performances of REC or CSC (e.g. self-consumed energy in respect to the total energy consumption, energy fed to the grid over the energy withdrawal from the network)	X	X	X	X
Optimization	1	Optimal size of PV component	Identify the optimal size of PV systems	X			
	2	Optimal size of BESS component	Identify the optimal size of BESS systems				
	3	Different objective functions	Set different objective functions for optimization (e.g. the optimal size for self-consumption)				
	4	Different constraints	Set different constraints (e.g. minimum IRR, set maximum CAPEX for PV plant, the maximum size for each roof)				
Open	1	Open code	Availability of code under MIT license				
	2	Open access	Freely available				
	3	Assumption description	Full description of assumption for optimization				

aspects. These graphs provide a visual understanding of energy distribution within the REC and highlight potential areas for optimization.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In analyzing these energy modelling tools, it becomes evident that each of the four models examined possesses distinct inputs and outputs. However, the relevant observation is that these inputs and outputs are not consistently present across all models. In fact, an overview reveals that no single model encompasses all the inputs and outputs in their entirety. This finding underlines the inherent complexity of energy modelling

and highlights the need for a multi-dimensional approach to capture the diverse aspects of RECs. By acknowledging the varying inputs and outputs in each model and recognizing the absence of a holistic representation, researchers can work towards enhancing the comprehensiveness and accuracy of energy modelling methodologies. This realization serves as a valuable foundation for future research and development in the field, fostering the creation of more robust tools that encompass a broader range of factors, ultimately leading to more effective decision-making in energy planning and policy formulation.

The cross-analysis between the four different tools allow the creation of a graphical representation of the functionalities. Figure 1 below shows the prevalence of input functionalities over all models. The output functionalities are present in all four models while the optimization is only performed by the GSE simulator only to find the PV capacity that fulfils the yearly consumption.

Fig. 1. Spider diagram of functionalities

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has successfully identified the most significant aspects involved in tools for designing RECs. The research has also revealed, through a cross-comparison of four open-access models, the need for improvements and enhancement.

The absence of input assumptions restricts the potential for knowledge advancement. The lack of detailed information regarding optimization techniques hinders transparency and the ability to enhance modelling potential. Therefore, future research efforts should focus on incorporating optimization techniques, thereby enabling a more comprehensive approach to RECs analysis.

Moreover, it is crucial to emphasize the importance of standardization in data collection, particularly where smart meters are not available. Standardized collection methods enable users to gather relevant data, thereby improving the reliability and validity of models. This standardization not only enhances the quality of the inputs but also enables meaningful comparisons across studies, promoting a more comprehensive understanding of energy systems and supporting evidence-based decision-making.

Furthermore, it is essential to acknowledge that RECs have often been approached as a singular entity in energy modelling analyses. To address this limitation, there is a pressing need to develop business models that cater to the unique requirements of different energy users. By embracing the concept of diversified business models, the energy community can move beyond the one-size-fits-all approach, resulting in improved efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and overall satisfaction for energy users. The establishment of standardized KPIs for impact assessment is essential in enhancing the comparability and consistency of

results across different modelling tools. This standardization would not only facilitate decision-making but also enable the benchmark and the sharing of best practices among different projects and studies.

Future advancements in energy modelling require open access to data and methodologies, and the establishment of standardized KPIs and data collection campaigns for impact assessment. These improvements would foster collaboration, transparency, and comparability, ultimately contributing to more informed decision-making processes and promoting the sustainable development of energy systems.

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